

A Study on the Relationship Between Learned Helplessness and Depression in Children with Cancer

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ABSTRACT

THIS JOURNAL INCLUDED IN MANY INDEXES, INCLUDING ADVANCED SCIENCES INDEX.
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This research is based on the level of learned helplessness and depression learned by patients diagnosed with cancer in the age 12-14 groups and their differences determined (age and gender). In the research, both learned helplessness and depression measurements were applied to a sample of 210 children totally, 98 of which are cancer patients, 112 of which are non-cancer children. The research shows both qualitative and statistical data. According to statistical results obtained from the research, significant difference has been determined between average score of learned helplessness of children with and without cancer. According to age and gender factors, significant difference has not been determined among average score of learned helplessness of children with cancer. Also, significant difference has not been determined between average score of depression of children with and without cancer. According to age and gender factors, significant difference has not been determined among average score of depression of children with cancer.

Also, according to qualitative results obtained from the research, dependence on mother at the age of 12, anxiety, pessimism and lack of self-reliance at the age of 13, loneliness and worry about future at the age of 14 are dominant feelings. While girl patients have been affected from the changes in physical appearance mostly, boy patients *have been affected from isolations of the society.*

Keywords: *Learned Helplessness, Depression, Cancer, Age, Gender.*

1. INTRODUCTION

There are around 120 new cases of pediatric cancer for every million children. As a result, there is an anticipated increase of 2,400 new cases of pediatric cancer per year in Turkey. There is now a full cure for 60–70% of children who are diagnosed with cancer. Patients who are detected early and caught at an early stage have a significantly increased likelihood of survival (between 80 and 90 percent). Cancers that occur in children are more prevalent among the poor and medium classes of society around the globe. In this case, the p53 gene, which is one of the genes that prevent the growth of cancer cells, either does not operate or acts less effectively (Yldz, 2008).

According to Topuz (2012), the incidence of cancer in children under the age of 15 fluctuates between 110 and 150 per million over the entire world. Approximately 130 people per million are affected by this condition in our nation. According to Topuz (2012), each year there are between 2,500 and 3,000 newly diagnosed cases of cancer in children in Turkey. In Turkey, there are roughly 600 new instances of leukemia each year, approximately 500 new cases of lymphoma each year, and approximately 400 new cases of brain tumors each year. These are followed by new cases of muscle, kidney, eye, and bone cancers respectively. It is recommended that patients who have been diagnosed with ALL, brain tumors, lymphomas, and bone tumors participate in the research. While cancer and other serious chronic diseases may create both physical and mental issues in children, the inability to maintain harmony or balance can also result in devastation. The child's equilibrium is thrown off, the child's sickness status is revealed, and the child's mental state is also affected by a stressor that is physical, psychological, and social. The impact that cancer has on a kid is contingent upon a wide range of factors, including the child, the family, the sickness, and the surrounding environment; these factors all interact with one another. According to Seligman and Maier (1967), the connection between the factors and the qualities of each component has the ability to influence the progression of the illness.

Common Psychological Problems in Children with Cancer

- Symptoms of a biopsychological nature, such as fatigue, discomfort, irritability, sleep and appetite disturbances, etc.
- An increase in attachment behavior, including dominating tendencies, connection to parents, and more
- Regression and introversion: behaviors such as thumb sucking, speaking in behavioral developmental stages, control of urine and stools, regression in self-care abilities, and the like
- Behaviors that are aggressive and based on taking action, such as a belligerent attitude and confrontational demeanor
- Nightmares and anxieties centered on one's health condition and treatment options, including preoccupation with retribution and dread of physical injury.
- Anxiety
- .

Reactions and Reaction Processes After Cancer Diagnosis

Shock: When a person is initially told they have cancer, they typically go through a period of profound shock. They have difficulty articulating how they feel because they do not want to trust individuals who have families who are afflicted with illness. It's possible that they repeat themselves, whether it be in the questions they ask, the things they say, or the material they wish to acquire. These are typical responses to the traumatic event that was had. When the diagnosis of the disease is given, it should be tried to be together with the mother and father, or to make a statement in the presence of one of their relatives (Pirl & Roth, 1999). If this is not possible, then the statement should be made in the presence of another relative.

Denial: When it comes to the act of denying something, some people would rather not be talked to at all, while others would rather have as little interaction with others as possible. It's not uncommon for patients' loved ones to try to brush the sickness and their worries under the rug. This is because people are terrified of cancer and it causes them to feel worried, and they talk about it. It is essential that people make an effort to comprehend one another's emotions and refrain from pressuring others to communicate if they do not appear to be open to doing so. It is imperative that you do all in your power to make him feel prepared to discuss his emotions and ideas with you whenever he is ready to do so.

Anger: The individual who is diagnosed with cancer, as well as his relatives, may have feelings of resentment against the illness, his closest friends, and his physicians. Even the sentiment of defiance might make its way to the forefront at times. It is possible to get more beneficial results by making an effort to comprehend that anger is a normal response, by not dismissing it, and by not reflecting it back on the person who is angry.

Feeling of Guilt: Patients and their loved ones want to know why they were diagnosed with cancer in the first place and may mistakenly believe that they, their ancestors, or their life experiences are to blame for their condition. They need to be made aware that cancer can be caused by a wide variety of factors, the majority of which are beyond of the patient's control.

Desire to be Alone: Being around a cancer patient might provoke a response from otherwise healthy individuals. "Why me and not someone else?" This is a question that is frequently asked. "Leave me alone" is a common sentiment voiced by both the sick and their loved ones.

Affected Status of the Child with Cancer According to the Stage of the Disease

Making the First Diagnosis: In childhood cancers, the first person to hear the diagnosis is not the child, but his family.

Period of Remission: It has been shown that when the sickness of the kid is under control, the parents' worry reduces, although it is typical for the parents to experience uncertainty throughout remission. It is possible for families to have denial and sadness throughout the remission phase of the disease because of the worry that the illness may return.

Relapse Period: With a return of the sickness, the child and his family may have the same strong reactions as they had when the disease was initially identified. If the patient is a kid, the recurrent status may be perceived as a significant amount of anguish, suffering, and persecution, and the child may feel as though they have been deceived. Every new development that takes place in the kid during this time period brings with it a sense of profound loss that the family must learn to live with. It is not sufficient to reject the gravity of the condition, and the worry of the kid passing away returns as a result of this.

Terminal Period: During this time, the family and the kid are aware that the child's chances of survival are decreasing, and the concept that "the end is almost here" provokes deep emotional reactions from both the family and the child. The following are examples of emotional reactions: anxiety, fear of the unknown future, helplessness, sadness, rage, and fear of becoming separated from life.

Learned helplessness

Learned helplessness is a state in which an organism is able to control a bad consequence through its actions; however, the organism does not conduct the behaviors necessary to control the outcome, or the organism is unable to learn the behaviors necessary to control the outcome.

Learned Helplessness in Cancer Patients

Cancer patients may experience feelings of melancholy, rage, non-adherence to therapy, and other behaviors that are not helpful to their recovery as a result of the fear of losing control and the learned helplessness that comes with receiving a cancer diagnosis. Interventions such as recording the patient's drug doses and helping other patients to cope with the side effects of the treatment increase the patient's active participation in the treatment, and may help to get rid of the loss of control and feelings of helplessness (Goldberg, 1981). The doctor presents the patient with options for his treatment. The patient is able to build sentiments of intellectual control and authority when they are informed about the diagnosis, the progress of the disease, and the treatment procedure. The loss of a patient's physical integrity or the amputation of a limb has a personal significance that has to be comprehended and discussed with the patient. Especially in the absence of effective rehabilitation therapy, difficulties the patient has with their ability to care for themselves, their mobility, their social life, and their function within their family might precipitate a depressed reaction.

The intellect, the wants, and the emotions of cancer patients are all weakened when they develop a learned helplessness. In addition to this, it results in three significant deficiencies. a decline in emotional stability, intellectual acumen, and motivation are the results of this. Patients with cancer who believe that it is not in their power to obtain what they desire, that there is always the chance of recurrence of the illness no matter how much therapy is given, and that the disease recurs, realize that utilizing their brains in the face of circumstances does not influence the outcome of the situation. Patients with cancer often struggle to express their feelings. A person who has struggled for a significant amount of time and who has been unsuccessful in their attempts to alleviate that suffering eventually comes to terms with the pain and learns to live with it.

Depression

According to Shors (2004), depression is the most frequent type of mood illness found in both adults and children. On the other hand, because it is a psychological condition, it is one that, with the help of professionals, may be properly addressed. In point of fact, depression is a typical response to the various stressful circumstances that might arise in one's life. It is possible for children to experience depression at a very young age; according to Çavuşolu (2001), the prevalence of depression increases throughout the transition from infancy to adolescent. youngsters that have poor levels of self-

confidence, are arrogant, and are unsuccessful have higher rates of depression than other youngsters. According to Çavuşolu (2001), many factors can contribute to an increase in suicidal ideation, including a deterioration in friendship relations, genetic predispositions, excessively oppressive and controlling family attitudes, parental conflicts and divorces, dissatisfaction with their physical appearance, loss of self-confidence, and domestic violence. In addition, another fascinating aspect of depression that is noticed in both childhood and adolescence is that it has been shown that the families of these children contain persons who have suffered and are now experiencing this sort of mood illness. This has been proven to be the case both in the past and in the present.

Depression in Cancer Patients

Depression is the most prevalent mental problem seen in people who have been diagnosed with cancer. The reported prevalence of the disease varies widely over a wide spectrum, from 4.5% to 58% of cancer patients. According to Kapçı (2004), it can be found in between 22% and 24% of inpatients. The fact that there is such a wide range of frequencies is likely attributable to the fact that investigations are carried out using a variety of diagnostic approaches and patient populations. Studies that did not employ a diagnostic and criteria indicated a significant incidence of depression among their participants, which included patients in their latter stages. Studies involving individuals who could discern between adjustment disorder and other mental health conditions and who were in excellent physical condition reported low prevalence rates.

Many sources of stress might be experienced by patients with advanced illness. In people who have advanced cancer, the likelihood of experiencing pain, sadness, and delirium is quite significant. According to Ozer et al. (1997), the rate of depression in advanced cancer patients is significantly higher than the usual prevalence of depression in cancer patients, which is 25%. According to Ozer et al. (1997), delirium is the most prevalent kind of psychiatric condition seen in settings involving palliative care, accounting for 28% of cases. Dementia comes in second place, accounting for 10% of cases.

According to Pirl and Roth (1999), individuals with cancer who experience pain are more likely to suffer from depression than patients who do not experience pain. The difference between regular sadness and depression is a person's tendency to feel an excessive amount of guilt and to have ideas that they are useless. The most prevalent source of worry in cancer patients is their inability to regulate their discomfort. According to Pirl and Roth (1999), a patient's experience of pain might be interpreted as an indicator that their condition is deteriorating, that their body is not responding to therapy, or that death is near.

2. METHOD

Purpose and Importance of the Research

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the differences and similarities between the levels of depression and learned helplessness in children of the same age, children of various ages, and children of different genders. This was accomplished by comparing the levels of depression and learned helplessness in children who had cancer to children who did not have cancer. It has been observed that not enough research has been done to establish the prevalence of depression and learned helplessness in children who have or have not been diagnosed with cancer. It is hoped that the information gleaned from sick children as part of this research project would prove helpful to medical professionals who work in oncology, as well as to educators who work with sick children and their families to offer support and education.

Modeling the Research Context and Its Limitations

In this study, a relational survey model served as the basis for the descriptive research that was conducted. For the purpose of this investigation, the cross-sectional methodology was applied to the collection of responses from pupils aged 12, 13, and 14. With the use of the relational screening model, their relationships with one another in various situations, such as cancer and depression, cancer and learned helplessness, age and cancer, and gender and cancer, were investigated. The purpose of this study was to determine whether or not factors such as age and gender had an impact on levels of depression and learned helplessness among participants. The relatives of the ill youngsters were asked for, and received, their consent (or approval).

1. The oncology departments of the various hospitals in the provinces of Ankara and Istanbul, where the application was submitted, were the only ones analyzed for this study, therefore its findings are restricted to those hospitals.
2. The elementary schools in Istanbul's various districts, which were the focus of the application, were the only ones for which the findings of the research were compiled.
3. It is dependent on the precision of the information collected from the surveys, which is one of its limitations.

Data Collection Tools of the Research

The "Learned Helplessness Scale for Children" and the "Depression Scale for Children" were both utilized in this research project. In order to obtain permission to apply the necessary scales for data collection, a written request was submitted to the relevant hospital in Ankara; a request was submitted to the Ministry of Health in order to obtain permission from the relevant hospital in Istanbul; and after the written permissions were obtained, the relevant hospitals were visited and work with children who had cancer got underway. These youngsters were evaluated using the "Learned Helplessness Scale for Children" as well as the "Depression Scale for Children." The researcher made the applications while working in the hospital setting for a period of three months, and the researcher made sure to inform the family of each kid who participated in the study about the goal of the research. The essential information on the application was provided, and the inquiries that the patients had regarding the application were addressed. As a result of the patients' susceptibility to infection, the appropriate safety measures have been adopted.

The researcher would next read the questions from the questionnaire aloud to the patients, and then he or she would record the patients' responses on the appropriate answer sheet. Patients who became nauseated or had discomfort during the application were given assistance, and the procedure was halted for as long as the patient desired to ensure that they did not experience any difficulties. In the course of the application procedure, information on the patient and the course of treatment was collected from the families. Interviews were conducted in a setting that was separate from the patient in order to accommodate those relatives who wanted to discuss their experiences and difficulties. In a similar vein, individual interviews with the patient were carried out in settings where the patient's family was not present whenever the patient expressed a desire to meet with a certain person. Patients and their families were given the chance, during individual interviews, to discuss sentiments that they were unable to express, conceal, or repress even to themselves. Sometimes this was done by sobbing, and other times through expressing hope. The technique of conducting interviews allowed for the collection of qualitative data that was not a part of the questions that were included in the exam. We were able to acquire information on a variety of topics, including the responses of patients both before to and following the receipt of their diagnoses, the impact of cancer and cancer on the child, the challenges encountered by children who have been diagnosed with cancer, and the struggle against cancer. It was seen that patients and their family exhibited interest in the data gathering tools, and they responded honestly to the questions that were asked.

The "Learned Helplessness Scale for Children" and the "Learned Helplessness Scale for Children" were administered to students in the 6th, 7th, and 8th grades in cooperation with the Principal, Deputy Principal, Counselors, and Classroom Teachers working at the school. This was done by visiting 4 primary schools, which were taken as a sample in the control group practices, between the months of March and May of 2012. Within one hour of class time, the "Depression Scale for Children" was completed. Both the students and the teachers were informed of the objectives of the research as well as its potential uses. It was noted that the pupils answered the questions thoughtfully and shown interest in the subject.

The results of the study were analyzed using the SPSS 15.00 package application. The scores that were acquired from the learned helplessness and depression measures were included in the quantitative data. These scales were administered to children with and without cancer. Techniques such as correlation and regression were utilized, along with descriptive statistical analyses such as the mean, standard deviation, and frequency distribution, while conducting a study of quantitative data.

The researcher categorized the qualitative data acquired from the experimental group based on the information gathered from children with cancer as well as age and gender factors. On the other hand, the researcher classified the qualitative data gained from the control group. After speaking with the patients, a list of the most prevalent issues that were found across all age ranges was compiled, as well as the frequency with which they occurred. The same approach was taken to compile a table that categorized common issues according to the gender variable, and the resulting frequencies were presented. Individual interviews with the patients' families were conducted, and the sentiments and ideas of the patients' relatives were also included in the study.

Scales and Reliability Analysis of Scales

The Cronbach Alpha coefficient was used in the research to analyze the results of the Learned Helplessness Scale for Children and the Children's Depression Scale in order to determine the degree to which their data were reliable. This coefficient is an internal consistency model that is based on the mean correlation among the scale items. It is expressed as a mean value. According to the findings of the study, the coefficient in question has to be more than 0.60 for the scale to be considered credible.

Learned Helplessness Scale for Children and Reliability Analysis of the Scale

First and foremost, the "Learned Helplessness Scale" that was established by Seligman and colleagues (1984) was modified into Turkish by Aydn (1985) and then standardized. It was once titled the "Children's Learned Helplessness

Questionnaire" when it was first created. The examination is done using pen and paper, and group participation is permitted. It is applicable to pupils in elementary school as well as students in secondary school. The form has been marked up with the answers. The application period does not have a time restriction attached to it. To use the scale, you don't need any specialized expertise at all. This scale is designed to assess learned helplessness specifically; it is made up of 48 items that are calibrated to measure internal, generic, and invariant attribution styles, and it is divided into three subtests. In each of the items, there is a scenario that might either be advantageous or disadvantageous for the individual, and in response to this scenario, the person is offered a choice between two different styles of attributing causality to the events that transpired. There are a total of sixteen questions included in the scale that are used to measure the different causal attribution dimensions. It is explored, using the questions relating to the internal-external causal attribution dimension, whether the individual attaches the causes of the events he meets to himself or to elements that are external to himself. It is explored, within the items connected to the special-general causal attribution dimension, whether the individual assigns the cause of the occurrences he meets to a reason that is particular to the environment in question or to a reason that is universal for all environments that are comparable to the one in question. On the other side, the items connected to the invariable-changeable causal dimension assess whether the cause of the events experienced by the individual can change over the course of time. On the exam, one point is awarded for each response that reflects the internal, unchanging, and general attribution dimension. On the other hand, no points are awarded for responses that represent the external, changeable, and specific attribution dimension.

The total number of points acquired in each category is added up to provide the learned helplessness score for that category. When the total score goes up, the number of times each subject uses the learned helplessness-specific attribution style goes up as well. The score of "0" is the lowest possible score on the scale, while the score of "48" is the greatest possible value. The minimum possible score to indicate the attribution pattern that is characteristic of learned helplessness is set at 23.

Aydin was the one to do the analysis of the scale's dependability. It was carried out using the test-retest procedure with an interval of four weeks in between each round, and the reliability coefficient was determined to be $r=0.83$ (Aydin, 1986). Aydin utilized the content validity approach for the research that determined the validity of the scale when applied to Turkey. The examination of the assessments of the specialists whose opinions were sought out for the purpose of obtaining this information revealed that the scale questions measure three causal attribution dimensions, which they intend to measure at an average rate of 96.1% (Aydin, 1986).

Depression Scale for Children and Reliability Analysis of the Scale

It is a self-report measure with 27 items that was developed by Kovacs (1981) and may be used with children ranging in age from 6 to 17. It is a form of self-assessment scale that is utilized in the process of determining the severity of depression in young people. It is possible to use it singly or with others as a group. Either the adult will read to the kid or the youngster will read it to themselves in order to fill in the scale. There is no time restriction at all. The youngster will select one of three possible statements from within each item by considering the events that have occurred over the past two weeks. Each group of sentences discusses the signs of childhood depression, such as difficulties sleeping and maintaining an appetite, as well as feelings of hopelessness and other negative emotions. The youngster is given three possible sentences to choose from, and they are to circle the one that best fits each situation. The supplied answers are assigned points ranging from 0 to 2, depending on how accurate they are. The following items are scored in the opposite direction: B, E, G, H, I, J, L, N, O, P, Ü, and V. The total of these scores is then used to calculate the depression score. The scale has a maximum possible score of 54; this is the greatest possible score. If your overall score is high, this suggests that your level of depression is rather severe. In our nation, the validity and reliability research were carried out by Belma Oy (1991), and the number 19 was chosen as the pathological cut-off point. The usefulness of the scale will be increased by the evaluation of the factor structure with patient groups. Studies to determine the validity and reliability of the measure were conducted on pupils in the age range of 9 to 14. In the analysis of the scale's reliability, the Cronbach Alpha internal consistency coefficient was found to be .77, and the test-retest reliability coefficient, which was acquired by applying the scale twice with an interval of one week between each application, was found to be .80. Both of these results can be found in the table below.

3. RESULTS

Children in the group of 14-year-olds who participated in the research made up 24.3% of the total. Participating in the research were 98 children (46.7%) diagnosed with cancer and 112 children (53.3%) who did not have cancer.

Quantitative Findings

Table 1. Learned Helplessness Scores (Overall) and Test Values

Status	n	Average	Std. Deflection	t	p
Child with cancer	98	23.5102	4.53451	3,437	.001**
Child without cancer	112	21.4018	4.34640		

**p<0.01

The "Learned Helplessness Test Average of Children with Cancer" has a score of 23,5102, which is greater than the "Learned Helplessness Test Average of Children without Cancer," which has a score of 21,4018. There was a large gap in the levels of learned helplessness exhibited by children with cancer and those who did not have illness.

Table 2. Learned Helplessness Scores and Test Values in Children with Cancer According to Gender Variable

Gender	n	Average	Std. Deflectio	t	p
Male	51	23.5882	4.79240	.177	.860
Girl	47	23.4255	4.28721		

Despite the fact that the "Learned Helplessness Test Average of boys with cancer" (=23,5882) is greater than the "Average of Learned Helplessness Test Scores of girls with cancer" (=23,4255), the two averages are quite near to one another.

Table 3. Mean Learned Helplessness Scores and Test Values in Cancer Patients by Age Variable

Age	n	Average	Std. Deflection	F	p
12 years old	34	24.4412	4.47343	1.120	.330
13 years old	38	22.9211	5.09043		
14 years old	26	23.1538	3.62979		
Total	98	23.5102	4.53451		

Despite the fact that "Learned Helplessness Test Scores Average of 12-year-old children with cancer" (=24.4412) were higher than "Learned Helplessness Test Scores Average of 14-year-old children with cancer" (=23,1538), "Learned Helplessness Test Score Average of 14-year-old children with cancer" (=23,1538). Children who have cancer also have a poorer "Learned Helplessness Test Average" (=22,9211) than the other two categories on average.

Table 4. Learned Helplessness Scores and Test Values in Children Without Cancer According to Age Variable

Age	n	Average	Std. Deflection	F	p
12 years old	26	21.6154	6.16491	.069	.933
13 years old	61	21.4098	3.49465		
14 years old	25	21,1600	4.14005		
Total	112	21.4018	4.34640		

While the "Learned Helplessness Test Average of 12-year-old children without cancer" (=21,6154) has a higher score than the "Learned Helplessness Test Average of 13-year-old children without cancer" (=21,4098), the "Learned Helplessness Test Average of 14-year-old children without cancer" has a score that is much lower. Children who have not been diagnosed with cancer have a "Learned Helplessness Test Average" (=21,1600) score that is lower than the mean of the other two groups.

Table 5. Depression Score Averages and Test Values in Children (With/Without Cancer)

Status	n	Average	Std. Deflection	t	p
Cancer Patient Child	98	12.1735	6.15944	-1,129	.260
Child without cancer H.	112	13.1964	6.87054		

The average "Depression Test Scores of Children with Cancer" is only 12,1735, which is much lower than the average "Depression Test Scores of Children without Cancer," which is 13,1964.

Table 6. Depression Score Averages and Test Values in Children with Cancer by Gender

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Gender	n	Average	Std. Deflection	t	p
Male	51	12.6078	6.32796	.725	.470
Girl	47	11.7021	6.00331		

The "Average Depression Test Scores of girls with cancer" are lower than the "Average Depression Test Scores of boys with cancer," which is equal to 12.6078.

Table 7. Depression Score Averages and Test Values in Children with Cancer by Age

Age	n	Average	Std. Deflection	F	p
12 years old	34	12.5294	7.00318	.103	.902
13 years old	38	12.1053	5.92653		
14 years old	26	11.8077	5.49195		
Total	98	12.1735	6.15944		

In spite of the fact that the "Depression Test Score Average of children with cancer in the 12-year-old group" (=12,5294) was higher than the "Depression Test Score Average of children with cancer in the 13-year-old group" (=12,1053), the "Depression Test Scores of children with cancer in the 14-year-old group" were higher. Also having a lower average than the other two categories is the group with the "Test Score Average" of 11.8077. The average depressive symptoms improved with increasing age, although only little.

Table 8. Depression Score Averages and Test Values in Children Without Cancer by Age

Age	n	Average	Std. Deflection	F	p
12 years old	26	12.8846	6.51354	2,741	.069
13 years old	61	14.3770	6.84876		
14 years old	25	10.6400	6.81224		
Total	112	13.1964	6.87054		

"Depression Test Score Average of 12-year-old children without cancer" (=12.8846) was lower than "Depression Test Score Average of 13-year-old children without cancer" (=14.3770), and "14. Depression Test Score Average" (=10.6400) of the children who do not have the disease also has a lower mean than the other two groups.

Table 9. Relationship Analysis between Learned Helplessness Scale and Depression Scale (general)

General	Learned Helplessness Scale
Pearson Correlation	.038
Depression Scale Shallow. (2-tailed)	.579
n	210

There is no correlation between the Depression Scale and the Learned Helplessness Scale. Both are independent measures.

Table 10. Relationship Analysis between the Learned Helplessness Scale and the Depression Scale in Children with Cancer

Children with Cancer	Learned Helplessness Scale
Pearson Correlation	-.009
Depression Scale Shallow. (2-tailed)	.929
n	98

It has been found that there is no correlation between the Learned Helplessness Scale and the Depression Scale in children who have cancer. In other words, the rise or fall in the learned helplessness score of children with cancer had no effect on the depression score of these children.

Table 11. Relationship Analysis between the Learned Helplessness Scale and the Depression Scale in Children Without Cancer

Children without cancer		Learned Helplessness Scale
Depression Scale	Pearson Correlation	.114
	Shallow. (2-tailed)	.232
	n	112

In children who do not have cancer, there is a marginally significant link between the Depression Scale and the Learned Helplessness Scale ($r = 0.114$). The significance value was calculated, and it was determined that the association was not significant because it was more than .05.

Qualitative Findings

In the study, participants had to be between the ages of 12 and 14, and there was a total of 98 children with cancer who took part. The patients and their families were each asked to participate in a separate interview, during which they were asked about the challenges they faced and the emotions they felt while undergoing therapy. The interviews lasted for around thirty minutes in total. In order to mitigate any potential adverse impacts that the patients could have on the family members, the interviews were carried out in a manner that was distinct from the patients themselves. The purpose of these meetings is to bring attention to some issues in addition to quantitative data in order to better reflect what cancer patients and their families go through and feel during the treatment processes of outpatients and inpatients. In addition, the purpose of these meetings is to shed light on the problems of children with cancer and their families.

Table 12. General Situation Evaluation Based on Age and Gender

Variables	Girl		Male
	Situation	Frequency	Situation
12 years (34 Patients) 17 girls, 17 boys	devotion to mother	12/17 (70.5 %)	devotion to mother
	Physically projected fear	10/17 (58.8%)	Physically projected fear
	introversion	12/17 (70.5%)	introversion
	feeling excluded	6/17 (35.2%)	feeling excluded
	Changes in physical appearance (weight gain, weight loss, hair loss)	12/17 (70.5%)	Changes in physical image (Weight gain, weight loss, hair loss)
	Don't feel sorry for being away from social life	8/17 (47%)	Don't feel sorry for being away from social life

The results of this study, gathered from a total of 34 patients aged 12 years old who took part in it, are presented in the table above. Attachment to one's mother is significantly stronger in males (76.4%), as opposed to females (70.5%). The percentage of girls who project their fear physically is significantly higher than that of boys (58.8% versus 47%). Girls (70.5% of the population) are more introverted than boys (58.8% of the population). The percentage of guys who report feeling excluded is significantly greater than that of girls (35.2%). Girls (70.5% of the population) are more likely to be affected by changes in their physical appearance than boys (52.9%). Because they are cut off from their social lives, boys (64.7% of them) are angrier than females (47%) about it.

Table 12. General Condition Assessment Based on Age and Gender (continued).

Variables	Girl		Male
	Situation	Frequency	Situation

13 years (38 Patients) 17 girls, 21 boys	physical anxiety	11/17 (64.7%)	physical anxiety
	Importance of appearance	15/17 (88%)	Importance of appearance
	Aggressiveness and pessimism	8/17 (47%)	Aggressiveness and pessimism
	Refusing to meet with their age group	5/17 (29.4%)	Refusing to meet with their age group
	Low self esteem	7/17 (41%)	Low self esteem
	Changes in physical image (Weight gain, weight loss, hair loss)	14/17 (82.3%)	Changes in physical image (Weight gain, weight loss, hair loss)
	Don't feel sorry for being away from social life	9/17 (52.9%)	Don't feel sorry for being away from social life

The results, which may be found in the table to the right, were collected from 38 patients aged 13 years old who took part in this study. Girls (64.7%) are more likely to report experiencing physical anxiety than males (57%). Girls believe that their outward looks are more significant than guys do (88.2% to 52.3%), respectively. Girls (47%) are less likely to exhibit aggressive and pessimistic tendencies than boys (47.6%). Girls are less likely to decline to meet with their age group (29.4%), but boys have a 33.3% chance of doing so. A lack of self-confidence is significantly more common among boys (47.6%) than it is among girls (41%). Changes in a person's physical appearance have a greater impact on girls (82.3%) than they do on guys (47.6%). Because they are cut off from their social lives, boys (80.9%) are significantly more disturbed than girls (52.9%).

Table 12. General Condition Assessment Based on Age and Gender (continued).

Variables	Girl		Male
	Situation	Frequency	Situation
14 years (26 people) 12 girls, 14 boys	Intolerance of restrictions on social life	7/12 (58.3%)	Intolerance of restrictions on social life
	feeling of loneliness	8/12 (66.6%)	feeling of loneliness
	Unwillingness	5/12 (41.6%)	Unwillingness
	feeling of loneliness	6/12 (50%)	feeling of loneliness
	Changes in physical image (Weight gain, weight loss, hair loss)	9/12 (75%)	Changes in physical appearance (weight gain, weight loss, hair loss)
	Don't feel sorry for being away from social life	8/12 (66.6%)	Don't feel sorry for being away from social life

The data that was acquired from 26 patients in the 14-year-old age group who participated in this study may be seen in the table that was just mentioned. Boys (71.4% of the population) are more likely to be intolerant of social life than girls (58.3%). The experience of loneliness is more prevalent in females (66.6%), as opposed to males (64.2%). Boys exhibit a greater degree of reluctance than girls do (41.6% versus 42.8%). It is more common for guys (57.1%) than it is for girls (50%) to have feelings of isolation. Changes in one's physical appearance have a greater impact on girls (75%) than they do on guys (50%). Because they are cut off from their social lives, boys (71.4% of them) are more upset than girls (66.6% of them).

Table 13. Evaluation of the Categories Obtained from the Interviews

* Opinions on medical personnel	Frequency (98 patients)
*Communication problems with medical personnel receiving psychological support	
“The psychiatrist only gives medicine, whereas I need a conversation.”	12 (12%)
“Medical staff sometimes make jokes about treatment that scare me, I'm afraid.”	7 (7%)
“Sometimes when I'm staying in the room, my mom and the medical staff are arguing, that's when I feel bad and get excited and upset.”	6 (6%)

Twelve (12%) of the 98 patients who took part in the study said that in addition to the medicine, they needed to have a discussion with the psychiatrist. Seven of the patients, or seven percent of the total, said that they were concerned about the jokes that the medical staff made regarding the therapy. Six patients, or six percent of the total, reported feeling dissatisfied as a result of the disagreements between the medical personnel and the mother.

Table 13. Evaluation of the Categories Obtained from the Interviews (continued)

* Problems related to the hospital environment	Frequency (98 patients)
Fear of the future: “As I see the patient lying next to me, I can't help thinking that I will be like that in the future too.”	12 (12%)
Difficulty of treatment: “I am afraid of going to back therapy.”	31(31%)
Fear of death and anxiety about the future: “I have friends who died, I miss them and I am afraid of dying too”	85(86%)
Financial problems: “My parents spend a lot of money on my treatment, I worry about my siblings”	13 (13%)
feeling of loneliness: “I miss my friends from school so much, I want to go back to school and spend time with my friends.”	67(68%)
“I feel left out here, I want visitors to stay longer, and I want more visitors to come.”	84 (85%)
Increased attachment to the mother: “I never want my mom to leave my side, I feel so lonely without her.”	77(78%)

It was said that 12 of the 98 patients who participated in the study had dread of the future because they witnessed people whose sickness worsened in the hospital setting. This represented 12% of the total number of patients who took part in the research. One-thirtieth (31%) of the patients reported being anxious about receiving therapy for their backs. Eighty-five of the patients, or 86%, reported that their friends who had passed away while they were in the hospital had an effect on them, and they developed a dread of dying as a result. Thirteen of the patients, or 13%, voiced their displeasure and regret over the fact that their families had spent money on their medical care. 67 of the patients, or 68%, reported feeling down because they were no longer able to attend school and that they missed both their friends and the atmosphere of the classroom. Eighty-four of the patients, or 85%, reported that they felt lonely and excluded in the setting of the hospital, and that they were saddened by the small number of visitors that came to the hospital. It was reported that the patients' bond to their mothers had become stronger in 78 percent of the cases.

4. CONCLUSION and RECOMMENDATIONS

It is believed that the quantitative data and qualitative information produced by assessing the impacts of this study on the levels of learned helplessness and depression of children with and without cancer can be helpful to those who are already working in this field as well as those who will be doing research in this area in the future.

- The mean score of children with cancer on the learned helplessness scale is greater than the mean score of children who do not have cancer, as indicated by the findings of the statistical analysis that was conducted during

the research. There is a statistically significant gap between the mean levels of learned helplessness in children diagnosed with cancer and the mean levels of learned helplessness in children who have not been diagnosed with cancer.

- Despite the fact that the mean score of boys with cancer for learned helplessness is greater than the mean score of girls with cancer, there is no significant difference between the mean scores of the two groups.
- The 12-year-olds have the greatest mean score of learned helplessness compared to the other age groups of children with cancer. No statistically significant differences were identified between the scores of children with cancer based on their ages when it came to their levels of learned helplessness.
- The group of 12-year-old children without cancer has the greatest mean score of learned helplessness compared to the other age groups. No statistically significant differences were identified between the learned helplessness scores of children without cancer when the age variable was taken into consideration.
- There is not a significant difference between the average levels of depression experienced by children who have cancer and the average levels of depression experienced by children who do not have cancer.
- There is no statistically significant difference between the levels of depression experienced by cancer patients who are male or female.
- The group of children diagnosed with cancer who are 12 years old had the highest average score of depression overall. There is no statistically significant difference in the depression scores of children with cancer when age is a variable that is considered.
- The group of children who are 13 years old has the greatest average score of depression compared to the other age groups of children who do not have cancer. There is no statistically significant difference in the levels of depression exhibited by children who do not have cancer based on their ages, as indicated by the variable.
- The level of depression is unaffected by increasing or reducing the amount of learned helplessness that a person has.
- The degree of depression in children diagnosed with cancer is unaffected by either an increase or decrease in the amount of learned helplessness in those youngsters.
- The degree of depression in children who do not have cancer is unaffected by the rise or reduction in the level of learned helplessness in those youngsters.
- In the group of 12-year-olds, the amount of connection to the mother and the level of physically expressed dread and anxiety are higher. • It has been noticed that introversion and the sensation of being excluded are at the forefront of the issue.
- It was discovered that there was a high degree of concern about physical changes in the group of 13-year-olds. This was a significant finding. It was more prevalent for patients in this age range to exhibit aggressive behavior, extreme pessimism, an unwillingness to meet with other people their own age, and a lack of self-confidence.
- Intolerance to the constraints placed on social life as a result of therapy, feelings of loneliness, hesitation, and dread of the future were noticed more frequently in the 14-year-old age group.
- It has been discovered that young women are concerned about changes in their physical appearance, particularly a loss of hair, an extreme reduction in weight, or an extreme increase in weight.
- It has been noted that males are concerned about being cut off from their social lives and restricted in their ability to participate in physical activities.
- Problems that are shared by all patients; The most fundamental requirement for all patients is to get ongoing psychological assistance. It was determined that every patient required ongoing psychological assistance.
- Children of all ages were extremely distressed since they had to spend their break from school apart from their pals.
- Patients often report feeling alone and alone while in the hospital.
- It has been noted that the relatives of the patients have a significant fear of losing their kid and feel weak and helpless in the face of the harsh treatment that is given to youngsters. This is due to the fact that the patients themselves are being heavily medicated.
- It has been noticed that it is necessary for the medical team to provide children who are undergoing treatment with specific information regarding their illness.
- Ensuring that children who have cancer are able to communicate effectively with medical staff; it has been found that these youngsters require sympathy, attention, and care.
- In consideration of the findings that were gathered from the investigation, the following are some recommendations for potential applications as well as directions for further study:
- In this study, the effects of age and gender variables on the level of learned helplessness and depression in children undergoing cancer treatment and their families in our country • This research was done out only in four separate schools in Istanbul, two hospitals, two colleges, and two public schools in two randomly selected regions in Istanbul and Ankara. • Future research will examine additional factors that may impact cancer patients. •

While conducting this research, variables such as socioeconomic level, family education level, disease duration, diagnosis, parental attitudes, cancer type and stage, and treatment duration were not included in the study. Similar studies were carried out with larger sample groups in different districts or different hospitals and schools. • In future research, the application is carried out with the same method to both the experimental and control groups (the researcher reads the questions to the child or the children read and answer the questions themselves), • Children with cancer in the oncology clinic, rather than talking about their emotional and mental problems, they are happy when they talk about their life, hobbies, and family rather than talking about their illness. Research, including studies on psychological assistance with patients, is being carried out.

- Communicating the gathered information to the relevant medical staff,
- It should be noted that the phenomenon known as "learned helplessness" has been the subject of very few research studies in the United States, particularly in the area of pediatric cancer. It is proposed that research of this nature be carried out, in particular in the field of pediatric cancer, and with the goals of identifying the factors that influence "learned helplessness" and "depression."

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